

NON-ISENTROPIC EFFECTS ON THE WRDC 20 INCH
HYPERSONIC WIND TUNNEL CALIBRATION

Melvin L. Buck
Alfred C. Draper

Aeromechanics Division, Wright Research & Development Center
Wright-Patterson AFB OH 45433-6553

ABSTRACT

An experiment was conducted in the 20" hypersonic wind tunnel to assess non-isentropic effects on the test section Mach number. Pressure measurements were made on a blunt 5° cone. These pressures were then compared with a Parabolized Navier-Stokes code to define the free-stream Mach number. The results indicate that the non-isentropic effects are not significant. There is no pronounced difference in the Mach number from that determined by the more conventional pitot pressure probe survey.

INTRODUCTION

Generally, improper characterization of hypersonic tunnel flow fields manifests itself as an error in Mach number. All hypersonic wind tunnels, regardless of type, appear to have some Mach number characterization problems. For example, AEDC's Tunnel C, heated by conventional clean air heaters, exhibits a Mach error of as much as 1.5 percent compared to that predicted by isentropic flow using the ratio of freestream pitot to reservoir pressure. These relatively small errors in Mach number can have large effects on the test article. It has been shown that a 2-percent apparent Mach error can produce a 20-percent error in static pressure measured on a model.

With the emphasis on computational fluid dynamics code validation and the generation of high quality detailed experimental data, the

ability to calibrate wind tunnel flows is of increasing importance. Even small errors in Mach number cannot be tolerated.

Reference [1] concludes that hypersonic wind tunnels operating above Mach 8 are likely to have flow-field characterization problems because of non-isentropic phenomena. Reference [1] postulates the mechanism is vibrational excitation, followed by vibrational freezing just downstream of the nozzle throat, and subsequent rapid relaxation in the downstream section of the nozzle. The de-excitation phenomenon is apparently enhanced by the presence of water vapor. It is hypothesized that such contaminants act as third bodies and collision of vibrationally excited air molecules with these third bodies allows de-excitation to take place.

For hypersonic wind tunnels, the reservoir gas is heated, by different techniques, to high temperatures which result in energetic states being excited. As shown in Figure 1, the vibrational state is excited starting at about 1400°R. This would imply that so called perfect gas wind tunnels which operate above about Mach 8 experience some degree of vibrational excitation which may affect the calibration. It appears that AEDC has been one of the few to examine this phenomena.

The approach used to determine this effect was to measure pressures on a blunt 5 degree half angle cone. The pressure changes can be substantial in terms of percentage but are relatively small in magnitude in this tunnel. This makes measuring with precision a challenge and takes all of our capability to precisely define the

changes in surface pressure. This will be the primary method used to assess the effect of the non-isentropic flow.

To determine the impact on the calibration of the 20 Inch Hypersonic Wind Tunnel, the experimental results are compared to CFD analysis to investigate the seriousness of the problem.

Tunnel Description

The WRDC 20 Inch Hypersonic Wind Tunnel (HWT) is an intermittent, blowdown to vacuum wind tunnel with an axisymmetric, 20 inch exit diameter nozzle contoured to produce uniform Mach 12 or Mach 14 flow in an open jet test section. The open jet length can be varied from 20 inches to 40 inches. The Mach number is changed by installing different throat sections, but using the same contoured portion of the nozzle. Air supplied to the tunnel is heated to 1700°R - 2500°R by an electrical resistance type heater with a maximum power rating of 1.5 megawatts. The high reservoir temperature is required to prevent any air liquefaction from occurring in the test region of hypersonic flow. The tunnel reservoir pressure range is 600 psia to 1000 psia for the Mach 12 nozzle and 1000 psia to 1600 psia for the Mach 14 nozzle. These reservoir conditions produce a test section freestream Reynolds number range of 0.6 million to 1.0 million per foot at Mach 12 and 0.4 million to 0.6 million per foot at Mach 14. Essentially this is a laminar flow condition which simulates flight conditions at Mach 12 and 14 from, 120,000 ft to 150,000 ft altitude. Run times are determined by the 100,000 cubic feet vacuum sphere and the pumping capacity of the three stage vacuum pumping system - 5 to 8 minutes of run time are usually possible. Between runs, the vacuum sphere must be pumped down usually requiring 10 to 15 minutes; therefore, 4 to 5 runs per hour can be made. A schematic of the whole system can be seen in Figure 2 and Figure 3 is a picture of the facility. The report by Gregorek in Reference [2] discusses the operational characteristics of the 20 Inch HWT in greater detail.

Model/Instrumentation Description

The model is a 5 degree blunt cone with a length to nose diameter ratio of about 29. The model has 27 static pressure ports located in the aft half of the model which will be the prime source of data to infer a free stream Mach number. One total pressure orifice is included in the nose along with another orifice which is used to eject neon gas to enhance the electron beam flow visualization. Figure 4 shows the model with pressure orifice locations noted. The model has interchangeable nose so that both blunt and sharp nose can be run.

The transducers used for the test are type 2238 1 MMHg Baratron and type DP15 validyne differential pressure transducers, there also is one absolute 2 MMHg Baratron type 122A transducer. The differential transducers used for the model static pressures were calibrated in increments of 200 microns up to 1200 microns (1.2 MMHg). The validyne transducer used to measure total pressure at the nose of the model was calibrated to 250 MMHg and the absolute transducer used to measure reference pressure was calibrated to .5 MMHg. The static pressure differential transducers were calibrated 20% higher than full scale because calculations showed that a 5 degree cone at Mach 12 and 1200 psi stagnation pressure would result in a static pressure up to 1.2 MMHg. Although these transducers were calibrated 20% over scale the plots of the calibrations were very linear, well within manufacturer's specifications of plus or minus 5 microns (.5%). Figure 5 shows a typical calibration curve for the differential pressure transducers. The tubing inside the pressure system and the model is made of stainless steel and copper, this type of tubing minimizes any outgasing effects that might occur. Figure 6 shows the transducer connections.

Data System Description

The 20 Inch HWT data system includes signal conditioning equipment, a data acquisition and control unit, a minicomputer and various computer input and out devices. Depending upon the type

of transducer used the output signal can go either directly into the data acquisition and control unit or uses some type of signal conditioning such as carrier demodulators. The Baratron transducers used in this test had an output of ± 1 Volt full scale and filter cutoff frequency of 200 Hz. They were read directly by the data acquisition unit. Each data point was actually an average of 100 readings. This was done to integrate out signal noise. Several validyne transducers were also used which required the use of carrier demodulators signal conditioner. These units have maximum output of ± 10 volts and contain filters set at 10 Hz.

The data acquisition and control unit is made up of a 72 channel multiplexer unit, a high speed voltmeter and various other input and output interface cards. The 72 channel multiplexer in combination with the high speed voltmeter is capable of a measurement rate of 100,000 reading/sec with auto-ranging. The high speed voltmeter has a resolution of 13 bits (12 bits plus a sign bit). It has an accuracy of better than 0.01% for the 10.24 volt, 2.56 volt, and 0.36 volt ranges and an accuracy of better than 0.15% for the lowest range of 0.040 volts.

The minicomputer system used is a Digital Equipment Company (DEC) Micro VAX III unit with 16 Megabytes of memory, a 450 Megabyte fixed disk and a digital magnetic tape unit. The data system outputs are displayed on several character display units which are updated once per second. The displays are used to display tunnel parameters as well as test data. Data is also printed out or plotted on a DEC LN03 laser printer. Figure 7 is a schematic of the data acquisition system.

Results

Figure 8 shows the model mounted in the tunnel in its test configuration. Also seen at the bottom of the photo is the transducer box. The test program consisted of running at a constant stagnation pressure of 1000 psi and varying stagnation temperatures from 1800°R to 2200°R in 100°R increments. Table I gives the

primary pressure data for the blunt configuration. From these measurements it is not obvious that a non-isentropic process is evident. However, there is a definite trend in the data up to 2100°R, but the 2200°R data does not continue this trend. The 2200°R data was re-examined and found to be without error. The results are typical conical flow except one would expect to see an increase in pressure at the aft end of the model which does not occur in this case.

To assess the non-isentropic aspects calculations were made using the WRDC Parabolized Navier-Stokes (PNS) code. The PNS code generates finite difference approximations to steady, three-dimensional solutions of supersonic flow over arbitrarily shaped bodies at high Reynolds number as long as there are no large subsonic or axially separated regions. It needs a starting solution as the initial condition with which to march downstream from a given axial location on the body. For pointed bodies, the code has the capability of generating a starting solution internally by using a conical step-back procedure. An unsteady Navier-Stokes code is used to produce starting solutions for blunt-nosed bodies as in this case.

The numerical method was originally developed at NASA Ames Research Center and further modified by WRDC. The governing partial differential equations are cast in a conservation form and the finite difference solutions are obtained by solving implicit difference equations noniteratively via local linearization of the flux vector. This method is due to Schiff and Steger (Reference [3]) who solved the resulting system of algebraic equations using the Beam-Warming technique [4].

The formulation of the PNS code was modified by Chaussee et al and was used extensively to solve for the flow fields about blunted cones, complex configurations, and other hypersonic applications. Various refinements including first-order, fully implicit body boundary conditions and a hyperbolic grid-generation procedure were incorporated in the code.

The stability of the marching scheme was considerably improved by Rai and Chaussee Reference [5] to fit the bow shock. They also gave the code an additional capability of using cylindrical coordinates as the base coordinate system which makes the code more accurate and efficient when applied to conical bodies. Additional refinements include dynamic step-size control, viscous contribution to forces and moments, an elliptic grid generator, inviscid flow option, and the capability to calculate initial data planes for sharp cone flows.

Using this code to compute the pressure distributions, it is possible to iterate on Mach number until the code matches the experimental results. This then defines the freestream Mach number. Figure 9 shows the results of the calculations with the experimental data and indicates the freestream Mach number is 12.29. Figure 10 shows this result compared to a Mach number distribution obtained using a conventional pitot probe survey. As seen in Figure 10, the centerline freestream Mach number determined from pitot pressure measurements is 12.22. Therefore, it would appear that the two techniques give the same Mach number within the accuracy of the measuring system. The pitot surveys result in a ± 1.0 Mach number. Figure 10 shows the Mach number distribution is not flat but has gradients at various locations, whereas the calculations assume a uniform distribution. That probably has a small effect on the results since this model is blunt and is influenced by a small portion of the centerline flow. The final analysis of these results do not support the contention of Reference [1]. In this case it would appear that the flow does not sufficiently depart from isentropic flow to significantly impact the conventional means of defining test section Mach number distribution.

Conclusions

The conduct of the test program and the results indicate the following conclusions:

1. Precision measurements are difficult and

require extreme care. Also they tend to display small problems in the facility which one must stop and "fix".

2. The results do not substantiate that non-isentropic effects are present in the WRDC 20 Inch HWT. The differences noted are within the measurement accuracy.

REFERENCES

1. Boudreau, A. H., and Adams Jr., J. C., "Characterization of Hypersonic Wind Tunnel Flow Fields," AIAA Paper 88-2006, May 1988.
2. Gregorek, G. M., and Lee, J. D., "Design Performance and Operational Characteristics of the ARL Twenty-Inch Hypersonic Wind Tunnel," ARL-62-392, August 1962.
3. Schiff, L. B., and Steger, J. L., "Numerical Simulation of Steady Supersonic Viscous Flow," AIAA Paper 79-0130, January 1979.
4. Beam, R., and Warming, R. G., "An Implicit Factored Scheme for the Compressible Navier-Stokes Equations," AIAA Journal, Vol. 16, pp. 393-402, April 1978.
5. Rai, M. M., Chaussee, D. S., and Rizk, Y.M., "Calculation of Viscous Hypersonic Flow Over Finned Bodies," AIAA Paper 88-1667, Danvers, Mass., July 1983.

FIGURE 1 - ENERGETIC SPECIES IN A WIND TUNNEL RESERVOIR

FIGURE 2 - 20-INCH HYPERSONIC WING TUNNEL SCHEMATIC

FIGURE 3 - 20-INCH HYPERSONIC WIND TUNNEL

FIGURE 4 - EXPERIMENTAL MODEL

sta	PRESSURE LOCATIONS							
	θ							
S/r_n	0	45	90	135	180	225	270	315
25	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
30	X							
35	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
40	X							
45	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
50	X							

FIGURE 5 - TYPICAL CALIBRATION

FIGURE 6 - TRANSDUCER CONNECTION

FIGURE 7 - SCHEMATIC OF DATA ACQUISITION SYSTEM

FIGURE 8 - MODEL INSTALLATION

FIGURE 9 - PNS COMPARISON WITH EXPERIMENT

FIGURE 10 - MACH NUMBER PROFILE ONE INCH FROM NOZZLE EXIT

TABLE I - Blunt Cone Data

$T_0(^{\circ}R)$	S/R_n	S/R_n					
		25	30	35	40	45	50
	$P_0(Psi)$	$P_1(Psi)$	$P_2(Psi)$	$P_3(Psi)$	$P_4(Psi)$	$P_5(Psi)$	$P_6(Psi)$
1800	1000	.0139	.0136	.0134	.0134	bad	.0134
1900	1003	.0142	.0138	.0135	.0134	bad	.0134
2000.6	1002.8	.0142	.0138	.0134	.0133	bad	.0133
2000.1	1004.1	.0143	.0138	.0135	.0135	bad	.0145
2100.9	1000.3	.0147	.0142	.0138	.0137	bad	.0138
2202.1	1000.6	.0143	.0137	.0134	.0134	bad	.0134